

Utilization of Technological Devices towards Personal Development of Senior High School Students

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ABSTRACT: The study aimed to determine the perception of the respondents in the Utilization of Technological Devices towards Personal Development of the Senior High School Students Percentage and mean were used in the statistical analysis of data. The study revealed that most of the respondents were female and 17 of Age, Smart phone was available gadgets and used WIFI connection; spent time 5 to 6 hours in using technological devices: The perceived utilization of the respondents in terms of Work Simulation, Class Collaboration, Information Searching, Game- Based Learning, Creativity and Innovation were found utilized. Likewise, personal development in terms of Physical, Intellectual, Social, and Emotional was revealed developed.

KEYWORDS: Personal Development, Physical, Social, Technological Devices, Utilization

INTRODUCTION

According to the article of Orbeta, A. et.al. (2019) which cited that the legislation of Republic Act 10533, or the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013 adds up two years to basic education. One of the foundations proposed by advocates of the law is that Senior High School (SHS) graduates will be equipped with skills and competence to work or participate in entrepreneurial activities if they choose to do so. Moreover, it is a necessity to assess the capability of the students, especially in different aspects of the personal development of the pupils as well as their performance in T.LE so that they can be capable of facing the reality of entrepreneurship[1].

In line with the school's vision and mission, the TLE Department aims to develop critical thinking, self-reliance, independence, culture sensitivity and entrepreneurship in the students by enhancing their skills on the different uses of technology and application of life skills. Education and training are one of the vital driving influences which is essential in the current situation of our country's development in economic, social, and cultural growth. Education performs a big role in improving and strengthening the creative and practical ability of human beings. Building on this, education is an instrument for creating knowledge, enriching living standards, as well as transmitting society's culture to future generations. As an essential component of education, Technology, and Livelihood Education (TLE) plays a vital role in the social and economic transformation of society. It provides trainees with the technical skills that position them to contribute their best to technological changes. (Morales & De Vera 2021)[2].

Given these reasons and concluded ideas, the researcher sought to know the importance of utilization of technological devices towards personal development and T.LE Performance which will serve as guide to the teachers on how they will deal with the fast change in new era of technology. The researcher would sincerely encourage and suggest studying the effect of technological devices in the personal development and performance which is being perceived to be a big help in addressing the techniques to be used in achieving a successful career training for the students.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

Determine the utilization of technological devices towards personal development of the Senior High School Students.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

A descriptive research design was used to determine the perception of the respondents on the technological devices and the personal development of the students. Possible significant relationship between the utilization of technological devices and students' personal development.

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Respondents of the Study

The respondents of the study were all TVL Senior High School Students in Lutucan Integrated National High School during S.Y 2022-2023.

Research Procedure

Conceptualization. When researching topics on utilization of technological devices in TLE the researcher and the adviser discussed several times. The researcher provided the panel members with the concept developed and prepared and inquired for suggestions to improve the paper's content.

Implementation. The researcher asked the approval of the research adviser to conduct this study and sought for the approval of the Oral Examination Committee. Upon the approval, the researcher prepared the researcher-made questionnaire which was validated by the two (2) experts namely Madam Crystal C. Marzo, Sariaya West District Research Consultant LAC 4 and Madam Maria Mina I. Razon, Master Teacher II of Lutucan Integrated National High School and three (3) TVL teachers also from Lutucan Integrated National High School namely Sir Wilson P. Feolino Jr, Teacher II, Sir Ronald B. Palamiano, Teacher II and lastly Sir Edmund M. Balasabas, Teacher III. Then, data gathering followed. The researcher secured first the letter of permission of the District Supervisor to conduct the study. Letters requesting for the administration of the questionnaire to the target respondents were given to the School Heads explaining that urgent responds would be a great help for her to have the needed information and data in her study. The respondents answer the survey with the use of researcher made questionnaire. Afterwards, transcription of the survey and analysis of results of the study were done using Quantitative method. Then the data were collated, tallied, and statistically treated. The tabulation, analysis and interpretation of the data gathered followed.

Data Analysis. The data were gathered after the respondents completed the actual survey form. The researcher followed up the research instrument and kept track of the information acquired before passing it on to the statistician. The gathered data were statistically treated.

Ethical Consideration. The privacy of the research respondents was assured by the researcher. The study did not contain the names of the respondents. The collected data of the researcher through the actual survey form was kept in strict confidence. The data collected from the respondents were provided honestly by the researcher.

Research Instrument

The researcher employed the researcher-made survey questionnaire as the main instrument in gathering the data and information about utilization of technological devices towards personal development. This method was used to simplify data gathering.

Statistical Treatment of Data

All the data were gathered and analyzed statistically using the appropriate tools that include the following: Mean and Standard Deviation were used to assess the Utilization of Technological Devices towards Personal Development of the Senior High School Students. To determine the relationship between the utilization of technological devices and students' personal development Pearson Moment Correlation Coefficient was employed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 3. Distribution of the Respondents in terms of Age and Sex

Age	Frequency	Percentage
17	33	55%
18	19	31%
19	8	13%
Sex		
MALE	22	37%
FEMALE	38	63%
Total	58	100.00%

Table 3 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents in terms of age and sex. It reveals that thirty-three (33) or 55 % of the respondents in this study were 17 years old and only eight (8) or 13% were 19 years. With regards to the sex of the respondents thirty-eight (38) or 63% were female and only twenty-two (22) or 37% were male.

The result is like the study conducted by Morales & De Vera (2021) wherein there were more female respondents than male which is also related to the results of findings of Baterna et al., (2020)[3].

Additional to the result of the current study, which is also the same findings from Buctot et al., (2020) [4] that female respondents were dominant than male students.[4].

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Table 4. Distribution of the Respondents in terms of Available Gadgets Used at Home, Devices Services: Data/Wi-Fi Available, Time Spent in using Technological Devices

Availability of Gadgets	Frequency	Percentage
Basic Cellphone	9	15.00 %
Desktop Computer	4	6.67 %
Smartphone/Android/IOS Cellphone	46	76.67 %
Tablet	1	1.67 %
Laptop	0	0%
Data/Wi-Fi Available		
ADSL Connection	1	1.67%
Mobile devices	15	25.00%
Hotspot	2	3.33 %
WIFI connection	37	61.67 %
Broadband connection	5	8.33%
Time Spent		
0-2 hrs	5	8.33%
3-4hrs	19	31.67%
5-6hrs	22	36.67 %
7-8hrs	11	18.33 %
9-10hrs	1	1.67 %
11hrs above	2	3.33 %
Total	60	100%

Table 4 shows the frequency-percentage distribution of the respondents in terms of available gadgets used at home. Majority of the surveyed respondents utilized gadgets as Smartphone/Android/IOS Cellphone with the highest frequency of 46 or 76.67% while laptop got the lowest frequency 0 or 0% when it comes to utilization of gadgets. In terms of Data/Wi-Fi Available WIFI connection were dominant in this study with the highest frequency 37 or 61.67% and the lowest frequency was 1 or 1.67% for ADSL Connection. With regards to time spent in using technological gadgets, based on the results more than 5 hours' time spent in this study with the highest frequency 22 or 36.67 % while 3 to 5 hours spent in technological gadgets got the lowest frequency of 19 or 31.67%.

Based on the study of Carstens et al., (2016) cell phones, computer, tablets, free Wi-Fi, gaming systems and electronic-based toys are all the rage today in the society which is connected to the study of DiMartino & Schultz (2020) that every student surveyed had some form of screened device and had a cell phone [5]. In addition, Vu et al., (2019) the use of laptop or tablet of the students was able the students access the internet, digital course materials and digital textbooks of the students with technology device [6].

This implies that majority of the group used cell phones as available gadgets at home which is in agreement with the study of Abadilla (2016) that the fastest-growing smartphone market in Southeast Asia is in the Philippines [7]. Likewise, in the study of Francis (2017) students had several forms of technology and internet access in their home, but fewer than half of the students used that technology for work related to school [8].

However, on the results of the study of Gorra & Bhati (2016) that the ranking of positive and negative consequences differs in all the three cases of use of technology - computer with internet, laptop with internet and mobile with internet which is agreed by Internet Society (2017) [9].

According to the study of Carstens et al., (2021) the choices count and percentages for the minutes per day that students were involved in technology were as follows: 0-30 minutes a day was 12 (41.38%); 30-60 minutes a day was 7 (24.14%); 60-90 minutes a day was 7 (24.14%); 90-120 minutes was 2 (6.90%); more than 120 minutes a day was 1 (3.45%). The total count was 29.

Strom (2021) and Mowatt et al., (2018) have the same result as most students used the computer for more than 6 hours per day. Almost half of the students surveyed spent more than 6 hours viewing a screened device. stated in the result of her study that technologies are being utilized daily within the schoolsystems, which has significantly increased student screen time [10].

Table 5. Perceived Utilization of Technological Devices in TLE by the Respondents in Terms of Work Simulation

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. Inculcate sense of responsibility.	3.12	0.59	Utilized
2. Develop decision making skills as done in the simulation activity or in practical activities.	3.12	0.56	Utilized
3. Give long-term knowledge retention during actual applications.	3.07	0.55	Utilized
4. Provide to learn and develop skills in purposeful ways	3.25	0.63	Utilized
5. Create a safe environment for hands-on learning experiences	3.38	0.58	Utilized
Overall	3.19	0.35	Utilized

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Legend: 3.50-4.00 Highly Utilized, 2.50-3.49 Utilized, 1.50-2.49 Somewhat Utilized, 1.00-1.49 Not Utilized

With an overall mean of 3.19, the respondents show that technological devices were utilized in Work Simulation in TLE as shown in Table 8. This indicates that respondents utilized technological gadgets when it comes to Work Simulation in TLE. Lozano & Perez, 2022 proved that technological devices play an important role in class teaching to reform and explore teaching model in new era which promote activities in class in a positive mood which can be seen in the result of the study since the respondents agreed in the use of technological devices as work simulation [11].

Having the highest mean of 3.38 shows that most of the respondents utilized the technological devices which is used in Work Simulation in the creation of practical knowledge practices. Catane (2020) stated that apart from the typical challenges that every subject confronts, the difficulties of some skills in TLE such as laboratory and manipulative skills were especially difficult since it involves standard work room settings to be done. In such cases where physical experiment will not be possible, the use of computer simulations would be most helpful so that learners may fully comprehend the ideas and practices which provide to learn and develop skills in purposeful ways [12].

Furthermore, having the lowest mean of 3.07 indicates that utilization of technological devices is used for development of responsibility as well as improvement of skills. Dixon et.al., (2019) cited that through technologies increases self-confidence and provided a safe, non-threatening environment for teachers to reflect on their practice with the students. The researchers concluded that evolving technologies could offer practical alternatives to create classroom realism in any skills. [13].

Table 6. Perceived Utilization of Technological Devices in TLE by the Respondents in Terms of Class Collaboration

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. Share interests and discussed it on the group.	3.08	0.74	Utilized
2. Encourage teamwork to accomplish the activities given by the teacher.	3.25	0.68	Utilized
3. Develop higher-level thinking, oral communication, self-management, and leadership skills.	3.15	0.63	Utilized
4. Develop genuine learning experience from the group.	3.13	0.68	Utilized
5. Increase participation toward learning and boosted academic scores	3.13	0.60	Utilized
Overall	3.15	0.44	Utilized

Legend: 3.50-4.00 Highly Utilized, 2.50-3.49 Utilized, 1.50-2.49 Somewhat Utilized, 1.00-1.49 Not Utilized

As pictured out in Table 6, surveyed respondents show that technological devices were utilized in the Class Collaboration in TLE with the overall mean of 3.15. It indicates that technological devices in TLE in terms of Class Collaboration was utilized. This means that technological devices has become an important educational technology component in higher education all over the world which stated by Măt,ă et.al. (2021). The new generation of wireless technologies and mobile devices makes it possible for students to learn interactively, collaborate and share ideas with each other. [14].

Similarly, the surveyed respondents considering the highest mean of 3.25 indicates that technological devices in class collaboration were utilized in assisting teamwork which lead to accomplish the activities given by the teacher. With this, Dixon et.al., (2019) cited the goal of using conferencing technology to develop collaboration and increase access to classrooms. This become ways to set up web conferencing technology (computer, speaker/microphone system, webcam, and large flat screen on wheels) in classrooms which will help for class collaboration.

However, this study proved that utilization of technologies can be helpful for class collaboration which increases participation toward learning since the respondents have the lowest mean of 3.08. Ademiluyi (2019) added that there was motivation in teachers to integrate technologies in teaching like the use of smartphones teachers commonly used for proper learning interaction with students which led to the study of the findings of Sulisworo et al., (2017). [15][16].

Table 7. Perceived Utilization of Technological Devices in TLE by the Respondents in terms of Information Searching

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. Facilitate learning anytime and anywhere to impart and inculcate knowledge.	3.20	0.51	Utilized
2. Expand knowledge in reading using technological devices is the easiest way to achieved it.	3.15	0.73	Utilized
3. Improve the chances of succeeding in a career endeavor.	3.22	0.64	Utilized
4. Develop inter connected of the world as result of globalization.	3.10	0.66	Utilized
5. Provide better understanding of oneself and future career that led to success in different activities and assesment.	3.27	0.52	Utilized
Overall	3.19	0.36	Utilized

Legend: 3.50-4.00 Highly Utilized, 2.50-3.49 Utilized, 1.50-2.49 Somewhat Utilized, 1.00-1.49 Not Utilized

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Utilization as perceived by the respondents, of Technological Devices in TLE in terms of Information Searching are presented in Table 7. With an overall mean of 3.19, the respondents show that technological devices were utilized in Information Searching in TLE. This indicates that respondents utilized technological gadgets when it comes to Information Searching in TLE. This statement is concerning on how technological devices were utilized in terms of Information Searching which have been used in TLE. Gorra & Bhati (2016) expressed that the most observed positive outcomes of utilizing technological devices were direct messaging through chatting, lesson query about assignments, sending and receiving e-mails, research through browsing the net including data gathering by downloading files and sharing cultural experiences with others through internet. Among the negative effects listed by students were accessing social websites like face book, twitter etc. during class work, playing games, playing music, answering, and returning calls and downloading and using copyrighted material. It is further observed that incidence of positive and negative consequences varies with the use of technology.

As revealed by the highest mean of 3.27, respondents indicate that technological devices were utilized as to information searching which give channel for new understanding. Tang & Chaw (2016) proved that digital literacy for learning is more than just knowing how to operate technology but also having the right searching information management and critical thinking skills, as well as appropriate online behavior[17].

The lowest mean of 3.10 indicating that the respondents in the information searching have used devices to develop networking and linking in the world as result of globalization. In the study of Redmond (2015) the effect of growing student involvement with digital media information searching is to help students develop expertise, better understanding, skills, and personalities to live, contribute and develop in the 21st-century digital world[18].

Table 8. Perceived Utilization of Technological Devices in TLE by the Respondents in Terms of Game-Based Learning

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. Increase memory capacity that will easily remember the topics.	3.22	0.64	Utilized
2. Help to understand classroom rules as well as to follow the mechanics in the games which is commonly applicable in day-to-day activity and real-life scenario.	3.07	0.66	Utilized
3. Motivate healthy competition with the group.	3.15	0.69	Utilized
4. Leads away from stress and make you listen actively to class activities.	3.17	0.72	Utilized
5. Provide instant feedback from the topic discussed from the online games applied.	3.24	0.57	Utilized
Overall	3.18	0.40	Utilized

Legend: 3.50-4.00 Highly Utilized, 2.50-3.49 Utilized, 1.50-2.49 Somewhat Utilized, 1.00-1.49 Not Utilized

As can be gleaned from the Table respondents perceived the utilization of the devices with the overall mean of 3.18. It revealed that when it comes to Game-Based Learning the technological devices were utilized in TLE as proven by the respondents. With the highest mean of 3.24 the respondents indicate the utilization of technological devices in Game-Based Learning. Serrano (2019) indicated that when digital game-based learning is utilized that incorporates key game design elements (collaboration, choice, feedback) as well as instructional design, there typically is a positive impact on student engagement [19].

Likewise in the study of Khan et.al., (2017) and Hanghoj et.al., (2018) found that there was an increase in student engagement and make them participate actively in class activities when students were involved in digital game-based learning which is similarly to the present result of this study having the lowest mean of 3.07.[20][21]

Table 9. Perceived Utilization of Technological Devices in TLE by the respondents in Terms of Creativity and Innovation

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. Express own idea in certain activities.	3.12	0.74	Utilized
2. Help to explore the meaning of your own work and experience.	3.23	0.59	Utilized
3. Improve creative skills.	3.33	0.71	Utilized
4. Provide productivity thus help profitability	3.30	0.56	Utilized
5. Improve avenues through which people can express themselves	3.30	0.65	Utilized
Overall	3.26	0.42	Utilized

Legend: 3.50-4.00 Highly Utilized, 2.50-3.49 Utilized, 1.50-2.49 Somewhat Utilized, 1.00-1.49 Not Utilized

As pictured out in Table 9, surveyed respondents show that technological devices were utilized in the Creativity and innovation in TLE with the overall mean of 3.26. It indicates that technological devices in TLE in terms of Creativity and innovation were utilized. With the highest mean of 3.33 shows, that respondents “utilized” devices. As Limon (2015) asserted, ICT improve the excellence of learning as it encourages learner inspiration, mastery of ideas and growth of lifelong learning skills .[22]

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In addition, respondents utilized technological devices when it comes to creativity and innovation in TLE with the lowest mean of 3.12. To have an innovation in TLE, creative thinking must be observed.

Table 10. Summary on the Perceptions of the Respondents on the Utilization of Technological Devices in TLE

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. Reduces time on physical exercise.	3.17	0.67	Developed
2. Tracks my fitness activities.	2.98	0.75	Developed
3. Improves my diets.	2.65	0.82	Developed
4. Enhances beyond strategies and skills between individual and team sports.	2.98	0.68	Developed
5. Increases risk of depression.	3.05	0.83	Developed
Overall	2.97	0.43	Developed

Table 10 shows the summary on the perceptions of the respondents in the utilization of technological devices in TLE. It indicates that creativity and innovation got the highest overall mean of 3.26 which was perceived to be most utilized by the respondents. Meanwhile class collaboration obtained the lowest overall mean with 3.15 which is interpreted as still utilized by the respondents.

The above results show that respondents perceived that creativity and innovation are helpful when it comes to exploring the meaning of their own work and experience. This also improves their skills that make them productive. As Limon (2015) agreed that utilization of devices helps to improve the learning of the students.

Moreover, even though class collaboration got the lowest overall mean still found out utilized by the respondents. As Dixon et.al., (2019) emphasized that using technology develop collaboration and increase the participation of the class. It was also noted by Mayuga (2022) that technological devices aid in manifesting critical thinking, creativity, and collaboration in TLE [23].

Table 11. Perceived Personal Development in Utilizing Technological Devices in Terms of Physical Development

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. Reduces time on physical exercise.	3.17	0.67	Developed
2. Tracks my fitness activities.	2.98	0.75	Developed
3. Improves my diets.	2.65	0.82	Developed
4. Enhances beyond strategies and skills between individual and team sports.	2.98	0.68	Developed
5. Increases risk of depression.	3.05	0.83	Developed
Overall	2.97	0.43	Developed

Legend: 3.50-4.00 Highly Utilized, 2.50-3.49 Utilized, 1.50-2.49 Somewhat Utilized, 1.00-1.49 Not Utilized

It can be seen from Table 11 the perceived personal development in utilizing technological devices in terms of *Physical Development*. It can be depicted that the respondents' overall mean response of 2.97 indicates that there is Physical Development. Based on the result it is visible that with the help of technological devices it developed the Physical aspect of the respondents with the highest mean value of 3.17. It is supported by www.google.com that technology can be used to inspire people to engage in more physical activities and monitor their health status. It is said to be an important tool in the campaign of physical fitness programs. With this, Wahyuni et al., (2019) reminded that type of practice using technological devices can use serious health (physical and mental) issues [24].

However, the above results were related to the findings of Boz, (2020) which revealed that mostly women having 12.9% participating in the research and 38.4% stated that the use of technological devices sometimes inhibits them from exercising. However, 48.7% stated that there was never any obstacle. [25]

Respondents have a notion that utilization of technological devices in terms of Physical Development with the lowest mean value of 2.65, interpreted as "developed". This implies that surveyed respondents were able to develop the physical aspects. This is different from the study of [Alosaimi et.al., \(2016\)](#) revealed that utilization of technological devices has several harmful effects on a person's lifestyle (e.g., increased consumption of fast food, weight gain, low levels of engagement in exercise, and fewer sleeping hours. [26]

Table 12. Perceived Personal Development in Utilizing Technological Devices in Terms of Intellectual Development

	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. Helps me in improving critical level of thinking by searching and browsing from the internet.	3.23	0.67	Developed
2. Develops my skills in judging and conceptualizing which to be used and not be used information from the internet.	3.22	0.64	Developed
3. Develop my digital literacy.	3.23	0.72	Developed

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4. Promote proper use of gadgets during learning process and assessment.	3.22	0.64	Developed
5. Solve problems that is applicable to my personal experiences in the real-life scenario.	3.08	0.65	Developed
Overall	3.20	0.43	Developed

Legend: 3.50-4.00 Highly Developed, 2.50-3.49 Developed, 1.50-2.49 Less Developed, 1.00-1.49 Not Developed

Table 12 presents the summary on effects of utilizing technological devices in terms of *intellectual development*. Respondents had intellectual development which found that utilization of technological devices help in developing intellectual aspect of the participants with an overall mean of 3.20. Based on the findings, respondents may believe that it is to have established intellectual development, proper utilization of technological devices will be a great help. Carstens et al., (2021) pointed out that technology enhances many learning opportunities and allows for student comfort but can also be a tool that is too heavily relied on and can potentially affect student's fine motor development and problem-solving skills.

Based on the result, having the highest mean value of 3.23 which suggests that used of the technological devices show significant part in intellectual development as observed by the respondents especially in cultivating rational critical level. On the results of the study of Avila et al., (2021) recommended that computers and the internet should be available for students and teachers to be utilize in various resources in teaching which improve the students' critical thinking, motivation, and higher-order thinking skills [27]. Likewise, Ojales (2021) agreed with the later statement which proved mental attitude of students toward the subject should also take into consideration as a factor of students 'performance using technological devices. [28]

Furthermore, the lowest mean of 3.08 indicates that in intellectual development using technological devices with the application of actual situation in finding solution to the difficulties and challenges, will be a great help. In a study conducted by Sülzenbrück, et al. (2011) which was cited in Carstens et al., (2021) asserted the effect computer use has on motor skills, they discovered that using modern technology could effect changes in basic psychomotor and cognitive skills. The personal experiences of the respondents were also developed in terms of intellectual development through the use of technological devices. [29]

Table 13. Perceived Personal Development in Utilizing Technological Devices in terms of Social Development

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. Develop social networking with classmates which promote confidence.	3.27	0.73	Developed
2. Help to lessen anxiety and pressure.	3.10	0.78	Developed
3. Promote effective way of communication, learning and thinking.	3.27	0.69	Developed
4. Connect me to my isolated classmate and helps find supportive networks	3.23	0.62	Developed
5. Improve my good relationship with your classmate, teacher, and other member of the community.	3.30	0.70	Developed
Overall	3.23	0.45	Developed

Legend: 3.50-4.00 Highly Developed, 2.50-3.49 Developed, 1.50-2.49 Less Developed, 1.00-1.49 Not Developed

Table 13 pictures out the perception on the personal development with utilizing technological in terms of *social development*. With an overall mean of 3.23, respondents were developed socially in terms of the utilization of technological devices. This denotes that surveyed respondents were socially developed. Brillantes et al, (2019) the TVL track is the aspect of the Senior High School program that exposes the learner to attainment of noticeable skills, competencies and values that could be altered into economic bene fits. [30] Based on the results, having the highest mean value of 3.30, the utilization of technological devices developed the respondents in building harmonious relationship with others. Brillantes et al., (2019) It aims to give students with technical vocational training skills and academic know-how to prepare them for the needs of the community and the global workplace through highly trained competent teachers.

However, the lowest mean of 3. 10 indicating that respondents' utilization of technological devices help in reducing the fear and demands in terms of social development. Saunders & Vallance (2017) agreed that in child and youth populations, including, academic achievement, depression, and anxiety are some of evidences showing that screen time is related to numerous health is sues.

Table 14. Perceived Personal Development in Utilizing Technological Devices in terms of Emotional Development

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. Hinders in communicating people.	3.07	0.73	Developed
2. Develop effective ways for managing feelings.	3.08	0.59	Developed
3. Helps in recognizing my feelings and others' feelings.	3.12	0.64	Developed
4. Develop the necessary soft skills to collaborate effective with others.	3.18	0.65	Developed
5. Develop relationship skills.	3.22	0.72	Developed
Overall	3.13	0.45	Developed

Legend: 3.50-4.00 Highly Developed, 2.50-3.49 Developed, 1.50-2.49 Less Developed, 1.00-1.49 Not Developed

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Technological devices in terms of *emotional development*. Having the overall mean value of 3.13, personal development indicates that emotional aspect was developed by utilizing the technological device. Based on the results, respondents may perceive technological devices play a key role in personal development in terms of Emotional Development. Carstens et al., (2021) noted that teachers must have support, as they can see that students become more active, enthusiastic and give more engagement when the utilization of technological devices in the classroom was observed. In addition, educators also felt that students need more training with the provided technology to help promote more independence as well as develop skills in communication.

Based on the results above, technological devices when utilized develop relationship skills in emotional aspects of the students which attained the highest mean value of 3.22. Strom (2021) reminded that administrators, educators, students, and parents need to be mindful of the possible negative influences in the utilization of technological devices on student mental health, physical health, and learning. The different aspects that have been cited are needed in emotional development of the respondents with the proper use of technological devices. When mental health and physical health are stable it will be connected to the emotional health of the respondents that will develop skills in dealing with others.

However, respondents having lowest mean of 3.07, implying that there is emotional development in communication skills when developed.

Table 15. Summary of Perceived Personal Development when Utilizing Technological Devices in TLE

	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1.Physical Development	3.19	0.35	Developed
2.Intellectual Development	3.15	0.44	Developed
3.Social Development	3.19	0.36	Developed
4.Emotional Development	3.18	0.40	Developed
Overall Mean	3.18	0.39	Developed

Legend: 3.50-4.00 Highly Developed, 2.50-3.49 Developed, 1.50-2.49 Less Developed, 1.00-1.49 Not Developed

Table 15 shows summary of perceived personal development in utilizing technological devices in TLE. It can be depicted that respondents in the personal development having highest mean of 3.19 both in physical and social aspects were developed. Meanwhile intellectual development got the lowest overall mean of 3.15 however still found developed.

In personal development with regards to utilization of technological devices found out that both in the physical and social aspect of the respondents promote confidence and effective way of communication, learning and thinking. Similarly, as stated by Ong (2018) TLE Department requires to inculcate the principles of the students which will support them to become more economical and qualified individuals, with a sense of social awareness on influencing the community through good leadership and service. This also intends to develop their unique characteristics and skills to equip them in the professional world with consideration on fostering the love for God and country.[31]

Moreover, Avila et.al (2021) recommended that computers and internet should be available for both teachers and students to be utilized in various resources of teaching thus improve the critical thinking, motivation and higher order thinking skills. Likewise Ojales (2021) agreed with the later statement which proved mental attitude of students towards subject should also be taken consideration as a factor of performance of the students using technological devices.

Table 16. Relationship between Utilization of Technological Devices and Personal Development of Students in TLE

Utilization of Technological Devices	Personal Development			
	Physical Development	Intellectual Development	Social Development	Emotional Development
Work Simulation	.255*	.453**	.298*	.337**
Class Collaboration	0.121	.441**	.398**	.392**
Information Searching	0.112	.375**	.391**	.276*
Game-Based Learning	.328*	.327*	.300*	.281*
Creativity and innovation	0.154	.443**	.388**	.307*

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

*Correlation is significant at 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Evidently, the results show that the Personal Development of the respondents in terms of Physical Development have a relationship to Work Simulation with $r=.255$ and Game-Based learning with $r=.328$ while Class Collaboration $r=0.121$, Information Searching $r=0.112$ and Creativity and Innovation $r= 0.154$ have no significant relationship. Furthermore, findings reveal that Personal Development in terms of Intellectual Development, Social Development and Emotional Development have a significant relationship to Work Simulation.

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It can be gleaned from Table 16 that there is significant relationship between the utilization of technological devices and students' personal development as can be seen in Work Simulation, Class Collaboration, Information Searching, Game-Based Learning and Creativity and Innovation. Similarly with the results from the study of Perez & Lozano (2022) which showed that there is a relationship between the use of technological devices and students' academic performance.

As a result, the respondents must possess proper utilization of technological devices to ensure good impact on personal development to be used in the future chosen career involvement. In addition, based on the result of the study of Mayuga (2022) emphasized that the knowledge and utilization of Information and Communication Technology of the respondents were found to have a significant relationship with lifelong learning skills. The competencies of the students in Information and Communication Technology were also found to have a significant relationship with critical thinking, creativity, collaboration, communication, computer literacy, and career and learning self-reliance.

CONCLUSION

Since, it was revealed that the utilization of technological devices and student's personal development were related with one another, the hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between the stated independent variable and dependent variable is not supported by evidence, hence it is not sustained.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In the light of the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are offered:

1. The school administrations may integrate programs or Seminar Workshop before each school year to provide teachers and students proper knowledge on utilization of technological devices.
2. Teachers may have a mentoring session about proper utilization of technological devices and motivate students about the said conference.
3. Teachers may promote daily activities that involve utilization of technological devices which develop the physical aspect of both teachers and students.
4. Teachers may attend workshops on the use of technological devices in instruction for student's personal development.
5. Future researchers may conduct a parallel study about proper utilization of technological devices for personal development through action researches and teachers may also intensify the proper utilization of technological devices that will help in sustaining improvement of the performance of the students as well as their personal development.

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